

Improving Pupils' Understanding on Electrical Conductors and Insulators through an Action Research

Adilah Md Shah¹, Zuraidah Zulkifli², Noor Haliza Bajuri³

^{1,2,3} Science Unit, Desa Tasik Primary School, Malaysia

adilahmdshah@gmail.com

KEYWORDS

Conductor, Insulators, Instructional Innovation, Science Education.

ABSTRACT

This action research study aimed to improve Year 2 pupils' understanding of electrical conductors and insulators through the implementation of an instructional innovation known as KO-PEN Z. The study was guided by Andrew P. Johnson's action research framework, which emphasizes systematic inquiry through the phases of problem identification, reflective planning, action, and evaluation. A total of 185 Year 2 pupils from five classes participated in the study. Data were collected using pre- and post-intervention questionnaires, classroom observations, and teacher reflections. Findings revealed substantial improvement in pupils' conceptual understanding, with post-intervention results indicating 100% mastery across all assessed items. The study demonstrates that Andrew P. Johnson's action research design provides an effective structure for teacher-led instructional improvement and highlights the value of hands-on learning in primary science education.

Article history:

Type :	Received in revised form	Accepted	Available online
Research Article (Developmental & Educational Psychology)	31 st December 2025	31 st December 2025	26 th January 2026

1. Introduction

Primary science education plays a crucial role in developing pupils' early conceptual understanding and scientific thinking skills. However, abstract scientific concepts such as electrical conductivity often present challenges for young learners, particularly when instruction relies heavily on explanation rather than hands-on experience. Teachers frequently observe misconceptions and difficulties in pupils' ability to classify materials as conductors or insulators after instruction [1]. Action research offers a practical and reflective approach for teachers to address such classroom-based issues. Andrew P. Johnson conceptualises action research as a systematic inquiry conducted by teachers to improve their own practice through evidence-based reflection and action. Rather than seeking generalisation, Johnson's model focuses on local improvement, professional growth, and instructional effectiveness. Guided by this framework, the present study investigated how a structured hands-on intervention could enhance Year 2 pupils' understanding of electrical conductors and insulators.

2. Action Research Framework

This study adopted Andrew P. Johnson's action research design. According to Johnson, action research should be driven by a clearly defined classroom problem, guided by reflective planning, supported by systematic data collection and culminate in both a research product and professional sharing.

Fig. 1. Andrew P. Johnson's action research design.

The action research cycle began with the identification of a classroom-based problem. Classroom observations and reflective teaching practices revealed that Year 2 pupils experienced difficulty in distinguishing between conductive and non-conductive materials. Pupils also faced challenges in applying science process skills, particularly observing and classifying objects after conducting electrical experiments. In addition, teachers encountered practical constraints such as limited instructional time and the difficulty of preparing multiple testing circuits for classroom use. These issues highlighted the need for a more efficient, pupil-friendly, and hands-on instructional approach. Next is planning and data collection. At this stage, the teacher designed the research plan and selected appropriate data collection methods. Pre-intervention questionnaires were developed to

assess pupils' prior understanding of electrical conductors and insulators. The intervention using KO-PEN Z was planned to be implemented during regular science lessons through individual and group activities. Data collection strategies included questionnaires, classroom observations, and reflective notes, ensuring that evidence could be gathered systematically while remaining practical within the classroom context. Data were collected before and after the implementation of KO-PEN Z. Pre-intervention data revealed low levels of conceptual understanding, particularly in pupils' ability to identify and classify conductive and non-conductive materials. After the intervention, post-questionnaire results showed a significant improvement, with all items recording 100% correct responses. Classroom observations further indicated increased pupil engagement, confidence, and participation during hands-on activities. The analysis focused on identifying patterns of improvement and understanding how the intervention influenced pupils' learning rather than on statistical generalisation.

Based on the analysed data, an action plan was implemented and refined. The KO-PEN Z kit underwent several phases of modification to improve usability, including reducing its size, integrating instructional guides, and adding classification activity cards. These refinements ensured that the intervention remained responsive to pupils' needs and classroom realities. The action plan also outlined strategies for individual and group experimentation, allowing pupils to actively engage in observing, testing, and classifying materials. Findings from the action research were shared with colleagues, school administrators, and the wider educational community. The innovation and its outcomes were disseminated through professional presentations, innovation competitions, and exhibitions at school, district, state, and national levels. This sharing process aligns with Andrew P. Johnson's emphasis on producing both a research product and a professional presentation. Feedback obtained during dissemination informed further reflection and highlighted opportunities for extending the use of KO-PEN Z to other year levels and science topics, thus initiating subsequent cycles of action research. On the last stage a focused review of relevant literature was conducted to inform the intervention. The review emphasised the importance of hands-on learning, inquiry-based science instruction, and action research as a tool for instructional improvement. In line with Andrew P. Johnson's recommendations, the literature review was purposeful rather than extensive, serving to support instructional decision-making and justify the development of a hands-on testing kit to address pupils' misconceptions and learning difficulties.

3. Methodology

This study employed a teacher-led action research design grounded in Andrew P. Johnson's cyclical framework, which involves identifying a classroom problem, planning an intervention, implementing action, and reflecting on outcomes. Within this design, the teacher assumed the dual role of practitioner and researcher, systematically examining instructional practices within the natural classroom setting to enhance teaching and learning processes. The participants comprised 185 Year 2 pupils from five classes in a Malaysian primary school, all of whom were involved in the intervention as part of their regular science lessons. Guided by Johnson's recommendation that action research should be driven by focused and actionable inquiries, this study addressed the research question: How does the implementation of KO-PEN Z improve Year 2 pupils' understanding of electrical conductors and insulators?. To ensure a comprehensive and evidence-based evaluation of the intervention, data were collected using multiple sources, in line with Johnson's emphasis on methodological triangulation. These included pre and post-intervention questionnaires to assess changes in pupils' conceptual understanding, classroom observations to document pupils' engagement and learning behaviours during the intervention, and teacher reflective notes to capture instructional insights and emerging patterns throughout the implementation process.

4. Product Design (Intervention)

The design of the KO-PEN Z evolved through three distinct phases, primarily focusing on improving usability for students and increasing portability. Phase 1: Initially, the KO-PEN Z kit was large in size, designed in shapes resembling a pistol and a long cylinder. This initial design presented challenges for students who found it difficult to handle due to their small palm size. Additionally, at this stage, the device did not have a dedicated storage area. Phase 2: To address the handling issues, the size was modified to be smaller, and a specific storage area was created for the kit. This phase also saw the inclusion of educational aids, such as activity classification cards, as well as physical samples of conductors and insulators for testing. A user manual was also provided for both teachers and students to reference. Phase 3: The design was further refined to be even smaller and more compact, making the kit box easier to carry anywhere. A significant usability upgrade in this phase was printing the user manual directly onto the KO-PEN Z unit and its storage bottle, allowing for quick reference before use. Furthermore, the kit was expanded to include two types of KO-PEN Z units: one that provides feedback via light and another that uses a buzzer to emit sound.

Fig. 2. KO-PEN Z Science Kit.

Figure 2 above shown the evolutionary design phases of the KO-PEN Z an educational science kit created to teach students about electrical conductors and insulators. Initially, the tool was bulky and difficult for young children to handle, lacking a dedicated storage solution. Subsequent improvements introduced a more portable case, classification cards, and various test materials to enhance the learning experience. The final iteration features a highly compact design with instruction manuals printed directly onto the devices for immediate reference. These refinements ensure the kit is user-friendly, portable, and effective for classroom experiments. Figure 3 below shows the final product in this research.

Fig. 3. KO-PEN Z Science Kit (Final Product).

5. Data Analysis and Discussion

The findings from the questionnaire analysis indicate that the use of KOPEN-Z had a highly significant impact on Year 2 pupils' level of understanding of the concept of electric current. A total of 185 pupils from five classes participated in this study. Overall, the results demonstrate a marked improvement from the pre-intervention phase to the post-intervention phase, whereby all questionnaire items recorded 100% "Yes" responses after the implementation of KOPEN-Z. This clearly indicates that the intervention successfully enhanced pupils' mastery of basic science concepts in a comprehensive manner. For items assessing pupils' ability to identify materials that can and cannot conduct electric current, the pre-test findings showed a moderate and inconsistent level of understanding. Study shows that many students (and even some teachers) have incorrect ideas about basic electrical concepts such as current, voltage, circuits, conductors, and insulators during science lesson [2,3]. For example, in this study only 40% of pupils knew that wood does not conduct electricity, and only 40% were able to name two materials that can conduct electric current prior to the intervention.

This situation reflects the presence of conceptual misunderstandings among pupils. However, following the use of KOPEN-Z, all pupils demonstrated correct understanding, with improvements to 100% for both items, thus confirming the effectiveness of KOPEN-Z in correcting science misconceptions. In addition, the findings also show improvements in learning experiences through experimental activities. Before the intervention, only 66% of pupils reported having conducted an electricity experiment. After the implementation of KOPEN-Z, all pupils reported having carried out such experiments. This suggests that KOPEN-Z not only enhances conceptual knowledge but also strengthens hands-on learning and active learning experiences, which are highly appropriate for the developmental level of primary school pupils.

Reflection and observation data collected throughout the implementation of KO-PEN Z indicate clear improvements in both teaching effectiveness and pupils' learning experiences. Prior to the innovation, teacher reflection revealed several challenges, including limited instructional time to construct electrical testing circuits, pupils' difficulty in distinguishing between conductors and insulators, and weak application of science process skills, particularly in classifying materials after experiments. These reflections highlighted the presence of conceptual misunderstandings and the need for a more practical and pupil-friendly instructional tool. Following the introduction of KO-PEN Z, post-intervention reflections showed that pupils became more confident in identifying and explaining the properties of materials, while teachers experienced reduced instructional burden and smoother lesson delivery. Classroom observations further supported these reflections, as pupils were seen actively engaging in hands-on experiments, independently and collaboratively using KO-PEN Z to test real objects in their surroundings, and accurately classifying materials as conductors or insulators. Pupils also demonstrated high levels of enthusiasm, cooperation, and sustained attention during lessons, indicating increased motivation and meaningful learning. Overall, the reflection and observation data confirm that KO-PEN Z effectively enhanced pupils' conceptual understanding. Active participation and mastery of science process skills in learning about electrical conductivity can be seen in pupils lesson if implemented correctly [4,5].

In conclusion, the data analysis provides strong evidence that the use of KOPEN-Z is an effective instructional approach in improving understanding, learning experiences, and the ability to apply the concept of electric current among Year 2 pupils. The overall improvement to 100% across all items indicates that the intervention successfully achieved the intended learning objectives and has strong potential to be expanded for use in primary school science education.

6. Conclusions

Overall, the KO-PEN Z Kit innovation successfully enhanced pupils' understanding of the concepts of electrical conductors and insulators, as well as their mastery of Science Process Skills. This innovation demonstrates that creatively designed and purpose-driven teaching aids can have a positive impact on Science learning in primary schools. The principle of “*pupils do, pupils respond, pupils remember*” was effectively realised through the meaningful use of this kit in the teaching and learning process.

Acknowledgement

Dedication to all teachers at Desa Tasik Primary School who were involved in this research.

References

- [1] Aydeniz, M. (2010). Measuring the impact of electric circuits kitbook in elementary school children's understanding of simple electric circuits. *Electronic Journal of Science Education*, 14 (1), 1-29.
- [2] Gardon, R. M., Mendezabal, M. J. N., & Dimalanta, C. R. (2021). *Teaching and learning electricity: A study on students' misconceptions about electricity*. *Manila Journal of Science*, 14(1), 35–52.
- [3] Maulana, R., Anggoro, S., & Purwandari, R., D. (2023). Identification of electrical circuit material science misconception in class VI SD UMP Students. *Proceedings on social science and humanities volume 12 Proceedings of International Conference on Social Science*, 397-401.
- [4] Nordin, N.A., Nordin, M.H.A., Abdullah, N., Rahman, M.F.A. & Tao, L.J. (2024). Development of 'Equation Transformer Game Board' to Enhance Thinking Skills. In: Alareeni, B., Elgedawy, I. (eds) *Opportunities and Risks in AI for Business Development*. *Studies in Systems, Decision and Control*, vol 545. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-65203-5_74
- [5] Santana, Lisabeth Marie, Caitlin Hickman, Joshua Bilak & Chandralekha Singh. 2023. "Investigating and Improving Student Understanding of Conductors and Insulators" *Education Sciences* 13, no. 3: 242. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13030242>